
NISSIM EZEKIEL: Father of Contemporary English Poetry

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ABSTRACT

Nissim Ezekiel (16 December 1924- 19 January 2004) an Indian actor, a playwright, poet, editor and critic. His writings contained wit and satire. He dealt with the common themes and had a realistic approach towards life dealing with the social issues, customs, traditions and political issues like poverty and corruption in India. He was the father of postmodernism and modern poetry of India. Nissim was a prolific dramatist, broadcaster and a social commentator. He was a professor of English and a reader of American literature at Mumbai. He taught at various universities in India and abroad. He contributed essays, plays, poems and magazines significantly. He used literary devices like Symbolism, Metaphor, Simile and Satire to make his writings effective and insightful. His poems were discussed in national and international forums. Modernism came to Indian poetry in 1940 with his profound verse. "The Night of the Scorpion" which gained a lot of popularity. He was honored with the Padma Shri award by the President of India in 1988 and Sahitya Akademi award in 1983. His writings deal with the conflict between the modern and traditional ways of thinking. He discussed the fact that modernisation had influenced the lives of Indians. He gained a lot of name and fame with his incredible contribution in the field of English literature. He was one of the founders of modern Indian poetry.

Keywords: Modernism, Symbolism, Metaphor, Simile, Satire

Nissim Ezekiel

Nissim Ezekiel was an Indian actor, playwright, editor and critic. In 1924, he was born in Maharashtra. He was born in a Jewish community. He was educated in St. Xavier's College in Mumbai. He moved to London for his higher studies. He started his career as an English faculty at Mithibai College, Mumbai. He taught at various universities in India and abroad. He belonged to the genre of modern Indian English poetry.

Ezekiel was an assistant editor in 1953 for *Illustrated Weekly*. His works were related to mockery and amusement. The concepts of sufferings and exploitation were reflected well in his works. He wrote regular and free verse. His style was simple, precise and clear. Ezekiel was a mentor and a distinguished scholar. His works contained simple themes such as the rural life of Indians and the socio-political issues of India. He examined the psychological conflict of the people with regard to the poverty and sufferings. He wanted to eradicate the socio-political disparities of Indian society and worked for the development of society.

Works

In the *Night of the Scorpion*, Ezekiel dealt with Indian culture, customs, traditions and superstitious beliefs. *Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa*, a satire on the people going abroad for the sake of materialistic pleasures. In his collection of poetry *A Time to change*, he wanted to change mankind by means of harmony among all. His poetry exposed the different and typical situations and its impact on Indian society.

Ezekiel focused on the aspect of spirituality and laid a thought on the materialistic life which ended very shortly. He believed that the true identity of a man could be found through spirituality. He had shared his vast knowledge on the philosophical aspect of an individual and the ways to find solace from the internal and external crisis of the world. He had a keen observation on Indian culture, tradition, values and beliefs so his poetry contained the social elements of Indian society. His poetry emphasized the spirit of Indianness and morality.

Major Works:

- *The Discovery of India*
- *The Three Plays*
- *The Third*
- *The Unfinished Man*
- *The Exact Name*
- *Snakeskin and Other Poems*
- *Hymns in Darkness*
- *Latter-Day Psalms*
- *The Professor*
- *Case Study*
- *Poster Prayers*

As Ezekiel was born in a Jewish family, he faced a lot of racial discrimination in India. It was clearly known from his poetry. He wanted to spread unity in diversity among Indians. He wanted the Indians to grow intellectually, emotionally, ethically, socially and spiritually. He looked for the development of an individual and the growth of an Indian society. He loved mother India and wrote against the racial discrimination that was prevalent in his era. He wanted to eradicate the evils of society through his critical works on superstitions and beliefs of Indians. He composed meaningful and beautiful poetic verses. He was the father of post-independence Indian English poetry.

Nissim published the three plays - *Nalini*, *Marriage Poem* and *The Sleepwalkers*. In his plays, he discussed women's rights and freedom, gender equality, the concept of marriage and criticized modern Indian society.

Themes

Ezekiel writings contain the following themes:

- Alienation
- Quest for Identity
- Religious Equality
- Indianness
- Gender Equality
- Eradication of Social Evils
- Patriotism
- Spirituality
- Unity and Fraternity
- Ethical values
- Individuality
- Independence
- Rural and Urban sensibility

Ezekiel's poetic themes like alienation and Indian sensibility gained a lot of recognition in the genre of Indian modern Literature. His style was simple and tone was conversational. In order to deal with contemporary issues, he used similes and metaphors to expose the reality of human lives. He used both free verse and rhymed verse for his poetry.

His poetry deals with the concept of love, urbanization, marital issues and spirituality. He emphasized on the social equality and ethical perspective in his writings. He had a rational and an intellectual approach towards the issues of the society. He condemned the blind superstitious beliefs of the Indians. As a critic he satirized the evil practices of Indians. He promoted equality and progress of an individual. His diction, style, theme and irony were remarkable. The Indian English poets of the post-independence era followed his writing skills and gained a lot of popularity.

Ezekiel was the first poet to deal with the various forms of love such as the physical love and the spiritual love. He was popular for his love poems in the postcolonial era. His poetry contained passion, lust, failure in relationship, extra marital affairs, emotional crisis and a quest for an identity. The true feelings, inner conflict and the men-women relationship formed the theme of his writings. He focused on the critical aspect of an individual in order to resolve the societal issues and evil practices of India. His experiences shaped his writings. As a critic, he excelled in dealing with the issues of urban life. His writings influenced the readers to curb societal issues and work for the betterment of society. .

Literary Devices

Nissim Ezekiel used powerful tools such as literary devices to reflect the lives of the people and the societal issues. Literary devices enabled the readers to understand the theme more effectively and easily. It helped the poet to express his ideas clearly to the readers and enhanced their interest. Few literary devices are:

- Symbolism
- Metaphor
- Simile
- Imagery
- Myth
- Satire

The above literary devices were used by Nissim Ezekiel for making the readers understand the themes effectively. He used 'Symbolism' in his poetry. The technique of using Symbolism enabled the readers to understand his themes in a better perspective. It proved his excellent intellectual skills and artistic skills. Symbols made the readers understand the theme of his poetry in an easier way. The Symbols added meaning and relevance to the given context of his poetry in *Enterprise*.

'Metaphor' and 'Simile' were used in *Night of the Scorpion*. Metaphor provided similarity between two different things such as the scorpion in the poem was described as the evil one. Simile can be described as a comparison of two things with the usage of 'as'. In the poem, the peasants were described as the swarms of flies.

'Imagery', a descriptive language, was used in *Urban* to describe the city, roads and the traffic. It enabled the readers to visualize the images.

'Myth' in his writings reflected his spiritual and intellectual thoughts. He had religious tolerance and believed in fraternity.

'Satire', an irony, was used by the poet in *Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa*. The poet criticized modernisation and commercialization.

He used poetry as a medium of thought and reflection of the people and the society. Life, emotions, experiences, exploitation, identity crisis, struggles and sufferings were part of his poetic verses.

Awards

Nissim Ezekiel was honored with the prestigious awards for his contribution to English Literature. In 1983, he was honored with the **Sahitya Akademi award** for his collection of poetry *Latter-Day Psalms*.

In 1988, he was the recipient of **Padma Shri award**, a highest civilian honor from the Government of India for his great literary contribution.

Conclusion

Nissim Ezekiel was a prolific writer of modern English Literature. His unique style, the use of literary devices like Symbolism, Simile, Metaphor, Imagery, gained a lot of popularity and recognition in the world of Indian English Literature. His articles, plays and poetry had a realistic approach towards the contemporary issues of India. His works conveyed the message of unity, fraternity and progress of an individual for the betterment of our motherland.

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